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Reflections on the Political Thought of Niccolo Machiavelli

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Abstract

*As articulated in *The Prince* and *The Discourses*, Machiavelli's political thought can be said to constitute a particular philosophy of Politics. What we find in them (and especially in *The Prince*) goes beyond a particular programme for a particular situation. For the concepts and postulations employed are not just universals, but man in particular as, the most basic unit of analysis, is a product of time, society, condition and circumstances. In this paper, an attempt is made, through the use of qualitative method, to examine, evaluate and interpret the political thought of our author by conceiving its birth in his personal trouble and the way in which this cripple and skews his ontological and epistemological conceptions. The implication of his assumptions and postulations on the practice of politics, and in particular their connection with, and susceptibility to production of violence is explored.*

Introduction

If Machiavelli had had a prince for a disciple, the first thing he would have recommended him to do would have been to write a book against Machiavellism (Voltaire, 1755).

What is a man saying? What is he hiding when he says, what he says? (Nietzsche)

Machiavelli's political thought is widely perceived as a reflection and expression of an old society (Medieval Europe) pregnant with the new (Renaissance Europe). For with him, as Cassirer puts it "we stand at the gateway of the modern world" (in Donner, M. et al., 1967:485). This, to

be precise, is in terms of an attempt to repudiate an entire tradition of political thought associated with the mediaeval period in Europe. In Machiavelli's words:

I am well aware that many people have written about this subject. I fear that I may be thought presumptuous, for what I have to say differs from the precepts offered by others, especially on this matter. But because I want to write what will be useful to anyone who understands, it seems to me better to concentrate on what really happens rather than on theories or speculation. For many have imagined republics and principalities that have never been seen or known to exist. However, how men lives is so different from how they should live that a ruler who does not do what is generally done, but persist in doing what out to be done, will undermine his power rather than maintain it... I shall set aside fantasies about rulers, and consider what happens in fact (Machiavelli, 1988:54-5).

In *the discourses*, a similar theme is maintained: "I have resolved to open a new route, which has not yet been followed by anyone" (Machiavelli, in Donner, M et al. 1967:127).

Yet, in Machiavelli, there is more to what is given above. For since truth is what withstand the test of merciless criticism, one's account of history must be interrogated and subjected to thorough scrutiny, taking the socio-historical context into consideration, while simultaneously pushing and transcending its inhibiting frontier towards a form of inquiry and unmasking that seeks to take the margin and periphery of the dominant historical accounts (in their search for general and totalitarian explanation) as a crucial factor in grasping the irreducible complexity of human and social reality. This marginal factor is the personal dimension and interest which keeps resurfacing but simultaneously concealing itself in historical narrative and discourse. For as Campbell rightly observes (following Hayden White) narrative is central, not just to understanding an event but in constituting that event

(in Devetak, R. 1995:185). Furthermore, and most importantly for our own purpose as students of political theory, historical narratives also perform vital political function in the present: they can be used as resources in contemporary political struggles. For *the Prince* in particular is a masterpiece in opportunism. Our intention in this paper is not to embark on argumentum adhominem but rather to deepen our understanding of his writings by focusing on the impact of personal trouble on his thought and its connection with the celebration and production of violence in the polity. In addition, the implication of this on ontology, epistemology and practice of politics unavoidably warrants examination. Incidentally, realism is under hammer while the relevance of ethics and morality as a force in politics is re-affirmed.

Obviously, what we set out to offer is an interpretation in the broadest sense of the term focusing on “why is the work made” rather than its historicity (a form of structuralism through which agency is denied or relegated to the background). For as Pierre Macherey argues:

a knowledge of the work is not elaborated within the work, but supposes a distance between knowledge and its object; to know what the writer is saying, it is not enough let him speak for his speech is hollow and can never be completed at its own level. Theoretical inquiry rejects the notion of the space or sites of the work. Critical discourse does not attempt to complete the book, for theory begins from that incompleteness which is so radical that it cannot be located (1978: 84).

Biographical Formation

Niccolo Machiavelli was born in Florence in 1469. He receives his early education from a well-known teacher of Latin, Paolo da Ranciglione and may subsequently have attended the University of Florence. Without previous experience as a public office holder "he suddenly found himself installed both as head of the second Chancery and as Secretary to the main foreign relation committee of the republic, the so-called Ten of war" (Skinner, 1988: ix); becoming an

accomplished civil servant, expert in government procedures and fluent in both interpreting and producing official correspondence (Grafton, 1999: xx). However, the year 1512 saw the collapse of the Florentine Republic of Soderini, and the return of the Medici spelt the ruin of a political experiment in which he had played an active part (Chabod, 1958:135). Thus:

Coming under the suspicion of conspiracy against the returned Medici... (and) after being arrested and tortured, (Machiavelli) retired from the city to his small farm in the country a few miles away, where he tormented himself a new with his desire to return to the metropolis and to politics. Driven to despair by his exclusion from the world of politics, and clinging to the hope that his political skills might win back the position of power he had lost (Grafton, 1999: xxi).

In a letter to his friend, Francesco Veltori, Machiavelli left no one in doubt with regard to his trouble and painful experience as well as his desperate desire to win the favour of the Medici ruling family by offering them his work-*The Prince* - a manual for success in the art of governance. Hear him:

I am at my farm; and, since my last misfortunes, have not been in Florence for twenty days. I rise with sun, and go into a wood of mine that is being cut, where I remain for two hours inspecting the work of the previous day and conversing with the wood cutters ... this brings me to dinner time, when I join my family and eat the poor produce of my farm... but when evening falls I go home and enter my study... for four hours space I feel no annoyance, forget all care; poverty cannot frighten, nor death appall me... (in Donner, M. et al 1967: 482-3).

The fruit of such intellectual labour from this man of experience is *The Prince*. He continues:

I am prompted to present it by the necessity which pursues me, seeing that I am consuming myself in idleness, and I cannot continue long in this way without becoming contemptible through poverty. I wish these

Signori Medici would begin to make use of me, even if it were only to set me to the work of rolling a stone... As for my book, if they read it they would perceive that the fifteen years I have spent in studying statecraft have not been wasted in sleep or play... (Machiavelli, in Donner, M et al., (ed) 1968:483).

Thus, even a cursory reading or perusal of his works would easily show the conscious and unconscious drive to present one's personal trouble in the guise of theoretical discourse, reflections and conclusions. In particular, *The Prince and The Discourses* are central to our attention because of their striking similarity and dissimilarity. Similar in the sense of embodying a "Paradigm shift" (to borrow from Kuhn) in the study of politics, but dissimilar in the sense that the former is animated by the spirit of monarchical absolutism, while the latter's weight and inclination is towards a republic. It is important to note that *The Prince* is generally regarded as Machiavelli's Magnum opus, probably associated with its novelty, provocativeness and timelessness. Yet, our biographical account of its author has shown that its birth is deeply imbedded in opportunism which, in turn, skewed and crippled its epistemological and ontological claims as we shall see later. For now, it suffices to say that our author begins his major political treatise with the end in mind, namely a position in which he could live the active political life he craved more than anything else (Grafton, op cited p. xxii, and Green, V, H. H. 1972: 56). Thus, the fall of the Soderini's regime in which he served was indeed the beginning of *The Prince* which in a pessimistic spirit anticipates the fall of man and consequently the dominant theological notion of man's depravity. Reaching a similar conclusion, Bronowski and Mazlish Posits that the Prince might never have been written if the Medici had not been restored to Florentine leadership (1963:48).

Politician, Courtier and Scholar

Machiavelli lived and experienced life in the heyday of Monarchical absolutism in Europe. Although he personally served a republic, such form of government had not acquired a firm root in the then Italian and

indeed European history and experience. For this was the era of one-man rule in which everything revolves around his person as reflected in court intrigue-the struggle to impress him by outsmarting your rival. In this race, great Renaissance painters, poets and writers were not exempted. Machiavelli was caught up in the search for financial and political patronage from the ruling aristocracy, the clergy, and the mercantile class. Whereas Michelangelo found Pope Julius II, Galileo found the Medicis as fat cows.

Evidently, our reading of *The Prince* and its dedicatory letter dearly shows how our author was skillfully playing the game of courtier-ship. To play this game, however, Machiavelli has to invoke the goddess of the truth. In his words:

I do not want to leave undiscussed an important subject about which rulers easily make mistakes, unless they are very shrewd and are skilful at choosing men. I refer to flatterers, who are found everywhere in courts; for men are so wrapped up in their own affairs, in which they are so liable to make mistakes, that it is hard to defend oneself from this plague... the only way to protect yourself from flattery is by letting it be known that being told the truth does not offend you (1988:81).

Paradoxically, the attempt to please and impress the Medicis by displaying his talent instead of strict discipline, loyalty and subordination has apparently instilled fear and insecurity to the medici-the power that be. For it may be seen as a taboo for a subject to have a sounder and more practical grasp of the statecraft than the very ruler he is desperate to serve. And what else could partly explain the story that (when) "Lorenzo was presented with *The Prince*, (he) preferred some greyhounds offered by another client" (Grafton, 1999: xiv). Sensing this, Machiavelli lament thus:

I hope it will not be considered presumptuous for a man of very low and humble condition to dare discuss princely government, and to lay down rules about it. For

those who draw maps place themselves on low ground, in order to understand the character of mountains and other high points, and climb higher in order to understand the character of the plains. Likewise, one needs to be a ruler to understand the character of the people, and to be man of the people to understand properly the character of the ruler (1988:4).

Robert Greene give us a vivid account of how two striking personalities, namely Fouquet and Galileo, apply and transgress the fundamental rule of the game-courtiership. According to him:

All masters want to appear more brilliant than other people. They do not care about science or empirical truth... they care about their name and glory... Scientists are not spared the vagaries of court life and patronage ... their great intellectual powers can make the master feel in secure (1998:4).

For instance, the Sun King, Louis xiv, was known to be a proud and arrogant man who want to be the centre of attention at all times and who could not countenance being out done in lavishness by anyone and certainly, not his finance minister. Nicolas Fouquet, the finance minister, failed to understand his master. He organized a party, unprecedented in lavishness, attraction and attendance, thereby playing to the gallery. By this action, Fouquet "inadvertently unbalance the master's sense of self, poke hole in his vanity... make him doubt his preeminence" (Ibid, p. 3) and paid the price. His action occasioned Voltaire's celebrated remarks that "when the evening began, Fouquet was at the top of the world. By the time it had ended, he was at the bottom" (Ibid). And to succeed Fouquet, Louis choose Jean Batiste Colbert, a man famous for his parsimony and for giving the dullest parties in Paris (Ibid,p. 2) There is no doubt, indeed, that Machiavelli was a skilful diplomat and political expert. However, in the mastery of courtier-ship, he was indeed a mediocre. The term "fortuna" so dear to him, and which he constantly resorts to wherever his explanation begins

to falter, is too elastic and open as a tool of analysis. Precisely, it lacks economy of thought.

It is important to note that our author's theoretical speculation embodied a disguise aspiration towards self-preservation. Thus:

There are many who think therefore that a wise Prince ought, when he has the chance to foment astutely some enmity, so that by suppressing it he will augment his greatness. Princes, and especially new ones, have found more faith and more usefulness in those men, whom at the beginning of their power they regarded with suspicion, than in those they at first confided in. Poldolfo Petrucci of Sienna, governed his state more by those whom he suspected than by others (1988:74).

This should be understood against the background of Medici's suspicion of Machiavelli in connection with his involvement in an abortive conspiracy against them. This led to his arrest, detention, torture and his subsequent passionate desire to serve the Medici ruling family. We should note that some of his friends survive the change of government with relative ease. Obviously, a number of scholars (i.e. Haddock and Chabod, among others) have shown that the historical examples he used (for instance in the passage above) to support his general political precepts are mostly adhoc and without meticulous attention to their sources. Machiavelli and Bacon, according to Haddock, "were both more interested in the practical advantages which accrued from an acquaintance with history than developing new techniques for the corroboration of evidence" (1980: 32). According to him, it would be a misreading of Machiavelli to equate the illustration of precepts by apt passages of Roman history with strict empirical confirmation. His use of history was always selective specifying the detailed implication of his theory of politics (Ibid, p. 11). Yet, once the historical examples are shaky, the theoretical postulation becomes questionable. For the conclusion does not follow from the premise.

Tension and Contradiction in Epistemology and Ontology

In Machiavelli, there is a serious tension between epistemology and ontology, in particular his perception of human nature. For it is not clear how Machiavelli expect the Prince to take his loyalty and sincerity for granted. Certainly, the issue of trust is unconsciously relied on. But since the primary motive of writing *The Prince* was to win back some degree of trust and favour from the new Medici regime, what would constitute the ground for this master-servant relations without running into one of the several contradictions into which his rigorous realism leads him (Gaus, in Donner, et al., op cited, p. 484)? Put simply, how can he who preach against trust seeks and hopes to be trusted? How can he serve without being himself? This advocate of interest in the name of scientific objectivity was oblivious of the fact that self-interest knows no boundary. For it can easily shift to the highest bidder as in the case of the mercenary troops he vehemently denounced. The erosion of "collective consciousness" (to borrow from Durkheim) and ascendancy of anarchical self-interest may partly be explained by the gradual incursion of capitalism against the feudal mode of production and consequently his "exhortation to liberate Italy from the barbarian yoke". To reaffirm his sincerity and patriotism, he was noted for having said "no doubts should be cast on my trust-worthiness because, since I have always been trust-worthy, I would not now be prepared to become untrust-worthy" (1988:95). Expectedly, his appeal to the Prince-Redeemer fall on deaf ears (Chabod, 1958: 137). Thus, the very realism of the Prince defeats its own purpose. The redeemer of the chosen people is the outcome of their defeat (Reader in Donner et al., opticted, p. 484).

Machiavelli was thinking and writing within a tradition associated with Thrasymachus, Thucydides, and later Hobbes, Nietzsche, Weber and Morgenthau (among others). This is known as power theory. From his realism in particular, it was but a small step to the various doctrines of *raison detat* that flourished in the eighteenth century and a somewhat larger step to the glorification of the state as force, of might as right which reached its peak in the nineteenth century German real politic

conception of Machstat (Camileri and Falk, 1992: 30). In particular, *The Prince* became almost an article of faith in the hands of opportunist rulers seeking to aggrandize power, as in Hitler's appropriation of Nietzsche's "The will to power". In the same vein, it was reported that one of the three books kings Charles V read with great delight and had them translated into his native tongue was the prince and the Discourses of Machiavelli (Jacopo in Dormer et al., 1967: 513). Mussolini was credited to have written an introduction to *The Prince* (Bello-Kano, 1.2000:143). There is also the rumour that the neo-colonial military dictator, General Ibrahim Babangida, was under its spell (ibid).

Earlier, we have argued that *The Prince* embodied an opportunistic discourse which can be used to justify any government in power. For a similar line of reasoning was employed to justify the Abacha's Military seizure of power in Nigeria. Reminiscent of *The Prince*- redeemer in volatite Italy, Abacha and his spokesmen portrayed his military regime as a child of necessity, and hence, its rationalization. Note that in the *Eighteenth Brumaire of Louis Bonaparte*, Marx employed a counter argument to this opportunism against Proudhon's celebration of a coup detat. For:

Proudhon, ... seek to represent the coup detat as the result of an antecedent historical development. Unnoticeably, however, his historical construction of the coup detat becomes a historical apologia for its hero. Thus, he falls into the error of our so-called objective historians in their failure to demonstrate the circumstances and relationships that make it possible for a grotesque mediocrity to play a hero's part (1969:394-95).

Back home, Usman's verdict on the Shonekan's Interim National Government is equally applicable to Abacha's Military regime. Thus,

To understand the Interim National Government and the political project it was fabricated to implement we have to recognize that there was no political impasse at all. What there was, is political collapse.

The collapse of an arrangement and the desperate panicky measures to save it by those who made it and to take advantage of the collapse by those left out of the arrangement in the first place (in Maduabuchi, 2003:169-170).

Indeed, it is difficult to resolve the contradiction or reconcile the tension of the philosophical and historical, general and particular in his discourse. Although *The Prince* was composed allegedly on account of Italy's predicament, Machiavelli develop his typologies and put forward his precepts in wholly general terms (Skinner, 1988: xii).

Inspite of this, however, Anthony seems to provide an antidote to this suppose dilemma. For according to him:

A writer may be operating on more than one level of discourse. An author may indeed be, and almost invariably is, addressing himself to a localized audience and a particular political problem, but he may also deliberately be seeking a general philosophical answer, which he wishes to convey to audience beyond his own spatial or temporal milieu (1980:453).

In Machiavelli's case, however, he is obviously not cautious in his assertions. For there is no such thing as man with capital "M". It is this sort of thinking that Nietzsche saw as the "congenital defect of philosophers". In his words:

All philosophers suffer from the same defect in that they start with present day man and think they can arrive at their goal by analyzing him instinctively. They let man hover before them as an aeterna veritas, something unchanging in all turmoil, a secure measure of things. But everything the philosopher asserts about man is basically no more than a statement about man within a very limited time span. A lack of historical sense is the congenital defect of all philosophers (2008:12).

Ironically, and in a typical fashion of Tweedledum and Tweedledee, Nietzsche also take as an axiom, an article of faith and an explicatory principle, the will to power (drive to enhanced power) as the underlying propensity governing human conduct.

Ontology

The concept of ontology is used here to mean the way and manner by which, or how an actor/agent construct the political subjects and attributes and imbued them with purposes as essences. This construction, human, interventionist and arbitrary that it is, is posed as the inescapable condition of human existence ala *Hobbe's* anarchy problematic. In other words, ontology is about how political actors construct the political world and seeks its ground in human existential reality. In so doing, political actors seek to inscribe and diffuse their image of the political whose object is to efface its own origin, contradiction and particularity. Thus:

All values by the means of which we have tried to render the world estimable for ourselves and which then proved inapplicable and therefore, devalued the world-all these values are, psychologically considered, the result of certain perspectives of utility, designed to maintain and increase human construction of domination-and they have been falsely projected into the essence of things (Nietzsche's *The Will to Power*, in Sayyid, B. S. 1997:118).

Thus, Machiavelli's gloomy atmosphere of personal trouble, despair and social decay generates a negative conception of human nature in which men are generally "ungrateful, fickle, feigners and dissemblers, avoiders of danger, eager for gain (Machiavelli, 1988:59). In addition:

All men are bad and ever ready to display vicious nature, whenever they may find occasion for it. If their evil disposition remains conceal for a time, it must be attributed to some unknown reason; and we assumed that

it lacked occasion to show itself; but time, which has been said to be the father of all truth did not fail to bring it to light, that men act right only upon compulsion; but from the moment that they have the option and liberty to commit wrong with impunity, then they never fail to carry confusion and disorder everywhere (Machiavelli, 1967: 46-8).

For as long as “you benefit them they are all devoted to you; they would shed their blood for you; they would offer their possessions, their lives and their sons, as I said before, when the need to do so is far off. But when you are hard pressed, they turn away” (Machiavelli, 1988: 59).

But if men are what they are, how sure are we, that the prince-redeemer would not fall into their trap? For "men will always be of doubtful loyalty unless compelled to be faithful" (Ibid, p. 82). Nonetheless:

I have no doubt at all that he would be received with great affection in all those regions that had been inundated by the foreign invasions, as well as with a great thirst for revenge, with resolute fidelity, with devotion and with tears of gratitude. What gate would be closed to him; what people would work against him? What Italian would deny him homage (Ibid, pp. 90-91).

Ironically Machiavelli the idealist and optimist triumph over Machiavelli the realists and pessimist. Our author equally sought to exclude himself from human savagery. For it is his duty as an honest man “to teach others that good which the malignity of the times and of fortune has prevented his doing himself; so that amongst the many capable ones whom he has instructed, someone perhaps, more favoured by heaven, may perform it” (Machiavelli, 1967:478).

At this point, a number of questions are in order. For instance, was the situation in his society such turbulent throughout its history as to call for this perception of human nature and readiness for despotism in place of liberty? Was the situation the same in other societies before and

during the period in question? Is human nature static? What is the epistemological ground for this perception? How comes that both Locke and Rousseau offer a different and optimistic picture of human nature? It is important to note that the writer as a human being is a product of history, of time and space. But precisely because his social pathology of Italy was at fault:

The diagnosis was false. Machiavelli lived at a time when the crisis in Italy's history was at its height, and in reviewing and basing his theories upon the outcome of two hundred years of that history he exalted the virtue of an individual, the virtue of a prince, to the dignity of the supreme controlling factor of life. As a result, he attributed Italy's ruin wholly to the sins of her Princes. Inevitably, he failed to pin-point the origin and development of that crisis and in concentrating principally on the "cowardice" of mercenary troops, he passed outside the realm of truth (Chabod, 1957:137).

From Machiavelli's perception of human nature emerge his empiricism and pragmatism. His supposed knowledge of history serve as the rich mine of his empiricism, while his rationalist construction of human nature provides a general rule on which to base his science. Man's static nature become the solid ground/premise for prediction and conclusion. Against the doubting Thomases, he was noted for having said "many people thought things have change since the Roman days as though heaven, the sun, the elements, and men had changed the order of their motions and power and were different from what they were in ancient times" (1963:128, in Melville and Santoli). In other words; "men do not change either ideas or their method" (Machiavelli: 1998:98-99). Thus, the type of science Machiavelli worked to erect influence him to ignore the effect of culture upon men and to treat them, so to speak out of history. Consequently, his rationalism:

collided with the empirical part of his method. His desire to state general rules and principles came into conflict with his attempt to pay attention only to "what was". He

thought the fact confirmed his a priori postulates, but he neither drew his postulates from the facts nor tested the fact which supposedly tested the postulates. We see this in his use of Livy. Machiavelli used Livy constantly, without any real attempt ever to check his historical facts; indeed, Machiavelli simply used the ancient histories as the "given". Thus he saw, not "what was", but what his postulates told him would be there. His speculative theory prevented him from looking closely at the facts, and the erroneous facts made a shaky foundation for his science. (Browniski and Mazlish, 1960:53-4).

Power, Violence and Implication on Political Practice

For Machiavelli violence is, in the final analysis, definitive of political power. Hence, the importance of military strength to the acquisition and maintenance of power. Power is a paradox. It alone, as expressed in the capacity to inflict injury, cannot sustained itself. He who set out to establish the autonomy of the state through violence as the ultimate ratio, somersaulted, when the very survival of the state came to depends on the people, their values and morality which at first he seeks to suppress until the last chapter of the prince, a chapter which obviously become his cul-de-sac.

It is therefore not by coincidence that Machiavelli choose Cesare Borgia and Castruccio Castracani as his heroes. Cesare's ruthlessness and brutality, his reckless imperial ambition and consequently the enormous external hostility against him, his dependence on his father (the then pope) does not merit our author's censure (to use his favorite term). His action is endorsed on the pretext that he ought not to be blamed because his failure resulted from extra ordinary bad luck (Machiavelli, 1988:23). He elaborates:

He seems to me worthy to be held up as model, as I have done, for those who have risen to power through favour or luck or through the arms of others. For he could not

have acted differently, given that he possessed a great spirit and had high ambitions. Only two things hindered his schemes: the shortness of Alexander's pontificate and his own illness (1988:28).

Castruccio Castracani of Lucca is also celebrated and glorified by Machiavelli as one of the men who did great deeds if he is to be measured by the time in which he lived and the city in which he was born. In his life he was inferior neither to Philip of Macedon, the father of Alexander nor to Scorpio of Rome (and so he died in the same year of his age as they did, and he would doubtless have excelled both of them had fortune decreed that he should be born, not in Lucca, but in Macedonia or Rome (1992:139). But fortune (a term made scapegoat by our author):

..., growing envious of the glory of Castruccio took away his life at the time when she should have preserved it, and thus ruined all those plans which for so long a time he had worked to carry into effect, and in the successful prosecution of which nothing but death could have stopped him (1992:164- 65).

Obviously, the life of this celebrated hero ends with regret as his address to Pagolo Guinigi reveals:

If I could have believed that fortune would have cut me off in the midst of the career which was leading to the glory which all my successes promise, I should have laboured less, and I should have left thee, if a smaller state, at least with fewer enemies and perils because I should have been content with the governorships of Lucca and Pisa. I should neither have subjugated the Pistoians, nor outraged the Florentines with so many injuries. But I would have made both these peoples my friends, and I should have lived, if no longer, at least more peacefully, and have left you a state without doubt smaller, but one more secure and established on a surer

foundation. But fortune who insist upon having the arbitration of human affairs, did not endow me with sufficient judgment to recognize this from the first, nor the time to surmount it (in Machiavelli, 1992:165).

This should serve as a lesson to the reckless "imperial"⁷ ambition of the so-called World-Police man- The United State of America. With unprecedented ferocity, Machiavelli's objectification of power and glorification of its autonomous existence neglect its elasticity and hence the "ruthless glorification of power" (as Bello-Kano puts it) of the state power as force and violence, found in *The Prince and Discourses*. For the concept of power as Maduabuchi aptly observes "is a delicate and tragic phenomenon ... it is like an elastic thread (hence elasticity) which can be stretched to any limit, but which definitely will have a breaking point. At the breaking point, the thread cuts (obeys the laws of physics) and the men doing the stretching collapses" (in Dukor, M. 2003: viii-iv).

This is the lesson we have to learn from the fall of Borgia and Castracani. It is important to note that violence is to politics what doubt is to philosophy, a point also made by Campbell and Dillon (1993:7).

Conclusion

All along, we have engaged in the task of trying to locate the basis of Machiavelli's political thought in his personal trouble and social existence and how violence constitutes a fundamental principle for his conception of politics. However, it appears that we have merely engaged in a fruitless exercise. For Machiavelli remain elusive by arrogating to himself the privilege to speak from both sides of his mouth. This may entails saying what he does not mean and simultaneously meaning what he does not say. In a letter to his friend, his words left nobody in doubt:

For a long time, I have not said what I believe, nor do I ever believe what I say, and if indeed sometimes I do happen to tell the truth, I hide it among so many lies that it is hard to find (in Greene, 1998:321).

Then, where and in what does the safety of our epistemology lies? In other words, must we mean what we say? The safest answer is to be found in our actions and deeds. Obviously, it is to the celebrated remarks of Descartes that we must turn in order to rest our case. Thus:

In order to ascertain that these were their real opinions, I should observe what they did rather than what they said, not only because in the corrupt state of our manners there are few people who desire to say all that they believe, but also because many are themselves ignorant of their beliefs. . For since the act of thought by which we believe a thing is different from that by which we know that we believe it, the one often exists without the other (Discourse on Method III, 1997:8).

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